

The enthalpy of transfer ΔH_{tr} is calculated from the slopes of plots between the K_s values and the inverse of absolute temperatures for different salts. The entropy of transfer ΔS_{tr} is calculated from the relationship

$$-\Delta S_{tr} = RT \frac{d(\ln f/f_0)}{dT} + R(\ln f/f_0)$$

The values of ΔG_{tr} , ΔH_{tr} and ΔS_{tr} at 20° are also listed in Table 1.

Experimental results indicate that K_s is a function of salt concentration as also of the distribution ratio of the solute in aqueous and organic phases. The geometry and the polarity of the molecules also induce salt-naphthol specific interactions^{1,2,13} which in turn modifies the ionic influences on the water structure. It is well known that α -hydroxyl group in naphthalene is more reactive than the β -hydroxyl. This may lead to several enhanced interactions, viz. aggregation of α -naphthol in the organic phase and solvation of α -naphthol in the aqueous phase while salt-naphthol interactions may be reduced. Correcting for the concentration dependence of K_w , the solute dimerization constants in cyclohexane are found to be 603.5 for α -naphthol and 567.1 for β -naphthol. When similar modifications are extended to K_s values for cyclohexane-naphthol-salt solution systems, the trend persists. Interestingly however, the trend is reversed when the salt is KSCN. The $\log f/f_0$ and ΔG_{tr} values of the naphthols clearly reflect the interplay of all these effects.

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Synthesis and Bromination of 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl) chromone

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LITERATURE shows that no work on the bromination of 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone has been done. Further a large number of flavones¹⁻⁵ have been reported to possess antimicrobial activity. It was, therefore, considered of interest to study the synthesis and bromination of 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone.

2'-Hydroxy phenyl-6-methoxy-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone gave a yellow needle shaped compound m.p. 270° when heated with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol for 16 hrs. The compound did not give violet colouration with ferric chloride. Infrared spectra of the compound in nujol mulls showed a band at 1635 cm^{-1} due to carbonyl group⁶. Therefore, 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone structure was assigned to it. The same compound was also prepared by debromination of 2'-hydroxy phenyl- α - β -dibromo- β -2-methoxy-1-naphthyl ethyl ketone⁷. Wheeler *et al*⁷ prepared this flavone and reported m.p. 178°.

With one or three moles of bromine in acetic acid 2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone yielded a dibromo derivative which on alkaline hydrolysis gave the known 3,5-dibromo-salicylic acid. The dibromo flavone showed an infrared band at 1660 cm^{-1} due to carbonyl group⁶. 6,8-Dibromo-2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone structure was therefore assigned to it.

Experimental

2-(2'-Methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone : 2'-Hydroxy phenyl-6-methoxy-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone (1 g), selenium dioxide (1.5 g) and amyl alcohol (15 ml) were refluxed on a oil bath at 135 to 145° for 16 hrs. A yellow product was obtained on cooling which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave golden yellow needles (0.6 g) m.p. 270° (Found : C, 78.98 ; H, 4.17. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 79.47 ; H, 4.63%).

2-Hydroxy phenyl- α - β -dibromo- β -2-methoxy-1-naphthyl ethyl ketone (1 g) was taken in acetic acid (15 ml) and potassium hydroxide (1 g) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on wire gauze for 8 hrs. The product separating on cooling was crystallised from glacial acetic acid. M.P. and mixed m.p. with the product described above was 207°.

6,8-Dibromo-2-(2'-methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone : 2-(2'-Methoxy- α -naphthyl)chromone (0.302 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (15 ml) and bromine in acetic acid (10%, 5.4 ml) added to it. The reaction

